

Coregistration of Airborne Synthetic Aperture Radar Data using Optical Flow

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Abstract

Coregistration has been a major concern in SAR interferometric and tomographic processing. The coregistration of real airborne SAR data is challenging in comparison to a spaceborne case. This paper focuses on the problems involved in the coregistration of an airborne dataset obtained from the Wachtberg imaging radar in X-band operated by Fraunhofer FHR. An analysis of the incidence angles and the coherence of each dataset will be used as a measure to understand the reason behind misregistration. We explore the possibility of computing displacements in pixels using existing methods from computer vision. These techniques are very popular for optical data. Here, we test their applicability to radar data with promising outcomes.

1 Introduction

Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) has been widely used in the area of remote sensing for analyzing and monitoring environmental changes. SAR tomography and interferometry have particularly gained popularity for such applications [1] [2]. The first and most crucial step in SAR tomography and interferometry is coregistration.

In general, registration is the process of matching two or more images of a particular region of interest obtained at different times from the same or a different sensor or from a different frame of reference. The purpose of coregistration is to align the samples for phase differencing and an imprecise repeat pass geometry makes the coregistration process more difficult [3]. When using experimental airborne SAR image pairs for interferometry, the image products are often not accurately georeferenced and the trajectories may not be parallel, nor straight. Besides, conventional techniques for registering satellite-based SAR images cannot be directly applied to airborne SAR images [4].

Coregistration without prior geometric knowledge can be performed in two ways: 1) Intensity based coregistration and 2) Feature based coregistration. The most common and simple method of coregistration is to perform a cross-correlation between two SAR images [5].

Many computer vision techniques have been explored to obtain pixel wise displacements in optical images and have been used in various stereo depth estimation applications such as robotics, augmented reality, photogrammetry and video understanding [6]. In this paper, coregistration using computer vision techniques is explored for airborne SAR data. The dataset is obtained from the Wachtberg imaging radar in X-band (WIR-10) acquired by the Fraunhofer Institute for High Frequency Physics and Radar Techniques FHR. An analysis of the airborne SAR dataset and the implementation of computer vision technique is explained in

the following sections.

The final goal of coregistration of the real data is to perform 3D tomography and to reconstruct the data using various techniques which have been applied for the X-band TerraSAR-X data as mentioned in [7].

Figure 1 A general flowchart for intensity based coregistration.

2 Conventional methodology

The framework described in the fig. 1 is the traditional method for intensity-based coregistration. The reference image and the secondary image are first roughly coregistered up to 1 or 2 pixels accuracy using the cross-correlation method. For rough alignment, the secondary image is then shifted in the range and azimuth directions with respect to the computed offsets.

The next common step is to perform a fine coregistration on the shifted secondary and the reference image. Different

methods are followed in order to obtain sub-pixel offset points. Some methods perform an oversampling of coarse cross-correlation peaks, locating peaks to sub-pixel as seen in [8] while other methods use an oversampling of SAR image patches and locating the peaks by cross-correlation of the patches [3].

An offset in the range direction occurs after coarse coregistration and this is normally compensated using fitting transformation equations. The secondary image is then resampled using suitable existing interpolation methods such as nearest neighbour, four and six point convolution, bilinear or truncated sinc kernel as explored in [9].

Many intensity-based coregistration algorithms exist in the literature, each follow different techniques such as the interpolation free registration method [10]. This method is most commonly used in astronomical image processing to register low PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio) images. This method focuses on using the modified moment to obtain the shift in sub-pixels.

Conventional image registration algorithms have proven to be inaccurate, time-consuming, and unfeasible due to image complexity which makes it cumbersome or even impossible to discern the appropriate control points [11].

3 Airborne SAR Dataset

The SAR raw data was collected by the Wachtberg Imaging Radar (WIR-10), an X-band radar sensor operated by the Fraunhofer FHR. The sensor was mounted on an aircraft and recorded the SAR echoes of a scene while it was passing eight different tracks in succession. The scene is located nearby the University of Siegen, Germany centered at 50.913N and 8.047E. The sensor has a local frequency of 9.8 GHz and a bandwidth of 500 MHz. The scene size is 400 m in range and 300 m in azimuth.

The dataset used for coregistration consists of complex SAR images that were reconstructed by a stripmap back-projection processor which is operated by the Fraunhofer FHR. The flight tracks were planned to lead to a tomographic data stack by flying straight parallel courses at different heights varying in the range of 48.3 m. As the real flight tracks are neither straight nor parallel, the information to evaluate the synthetic apertures for each scene position is attached to the SAR images. Weighting in range and azimuth has been applied to reduce side lobes.

3.1 Data Analysis

The main focus for the dataset provided is to perform interferometric and tomographic SAR processing. SAR tomography generates 3D images by exploiting a repeat pass of the radar sensor. Target acquisitions are carried out at different incidence angles by the radar sensor. This means that a certain pixel in different acquisitions no longer indicates the exact point on the ground. The incidence angles for all the tracks of the dataset are as shown in Fig.2. As observed in the above graph, it can be noticed that the incidence angles for Track 1, Track 2 and Track 7 have a huge difference in comparison to the other tracks. The most important reason for this difference is the instability of the air-

Figure 2 Incidence angle over time for all tracks of the airborne dataset.

borne sensor and a fluctuation in altitude, course and side direction which also lead to additional errors in the dataset. This is not the case for a spaceborne sensor hence coregistration for a spaceborne dataset is comparatively easier.

Another reason for the misregistration of the tracks is the layover and foreshortening effect which is most commonly observed in SAR side-looking geometry as depicted in Fig. 3. The effect of foreshortening occurs when the area of interest is bent towards the sensor and the height of the vertical buildings appear to be on ground. The effect is clearly

Figure 3 Geometry of the foreshortening effect in SAR is shown for z axis against ground range r_g

visible in Fig. 5, Sect. 5, and can be calculated by using a reference height or a digital elevation model and the vertical and horizontal baseline information (see eq. 1 [15]).

$$\Delta r = \sqrt{(H + B_z)^2 + (\sqrt{r_0^2 - H^2} + B_y)^2} - r_0 \quad (1)$$

where, H is the platform height of the reference image, B_z and B_y are the vertical and horizontal baseline respectively and r_0 is the slant range of the reference image.

Coherence, in general, refers to the fixed relationship of waves in an electromagnetic radiation and two waves are said to be coherent if they are in phase [13]. For the case of SAR interferometry, coherence is a parameter which measures the phase that is preserved in the received signal. The coherence of two SAR images u_1 and u_2 is given by the cross-correlation coefficient given by Eq.(2) [12].

$$\hat{\gamma} = \frac{E[u_1 u_2^*]}{\sqrt{E[|u_1|^2]E[|u_2|^2]}} \quad (2)$$

The following is the coherence matrix generated for all tracks before coregistration assuming each track to be the reference and the rest to be the secondary images.

$$\hat{\gamma} = \begin{pmatrix} 1.00 & 0.23 & 0.26 & 0.26 & 0.28 & 0.27 & 0.29 & 0.28 \\ 0.23 & 1.00 & 0.39 & 0.38 & 0.36 & 0.36 & 0.29 & 0.35 \\ 0.26 & 0.39 & 1.00 & 0.60 & 0.45 & 0.49 & 0.33 & 0.42 \\ 0.26 & 0.38 & 0.60 & 1.00 & 0.46 & 0.49 & 0.33 & 0.41 \\ 0.28 & 0.36 & 0.45 & 0.46 & 1.00 & 0.47 & 0.35 & 0.49 \\ 0.27 & 0.36 & 0.49 & 0.49 & 0.47 & 1.00 & 0.36 & 0.45 \\ 0.29 & 0.29 & 0.33 & 0.33 & 0.35 & 0.36 & 1.00 & 0.37 \\ 0.28 & 0.35 & 0.42 & 0.41 & 0.49 & 0.45 & 0.37 & 1.00 \end{pmatrix}$$

Coherence can vary between the values of 0 and 1 where 0 represents a complete decorrelation in the images, meaning that the interferometric phase is pure noise, while the value 1 represents a strong correlation and implies that the phase information is preserved. A physical interpretation is that it represents the fraction of power scattered by unchanged parts of the scene [14]. Coherence is a measure of the quality of the interferogram and provides subtle details or changes that have occurred in the image. Coherence imagery is able to detect centimeter scale changes in the scatterer distribution [13]. The coherence matrix as shown above indicates a sufficiently bad coherence for Tracks 1, 2 and 7 while the correlation coefficients for Track 3, Track 4, Track 5, Track 6 and Track 8 are comparatively better. An interferogram and a coherence map are presented for Track 4 and Track 6 in Fig. 4 and Fig. 7 respectively. The interferogram provides the phase difference present in the image. Fig. 4 represents the interferogram after coarse coregistration.

4 Optical Flow for Coregistration

The correlation analysis shows that Tracks 1, 2 and 7 are not well explained by a single translational motion for the complete image. Instead, locally variable deformations affect the acquired images mainly due to the parallax effect depicted in Fig. 3. Therefore, local coregistration techniques become necessary. While the images could be broken into patches, followed by a local correlation analysis, this approach is not very robust as shown in the context of Background Oriented Schlieren Imaging, a correlation-based image analysis technique [17]. Fortunately, the computer vision literature has produced a large body of work on the problem of coregistration, termed optical-flow computation [21, 20] in this community [18, 19], in the past 40 years.

Figure 4 Interferogram of the scene obtained from two SAR images of the WIR-10 airborne radar sensor

4.1 Optical Flow Primer

Optical flow computation rests on the principle of intensity constancy between two frames of, e.g. a video sequence, given a suitable displacement field $(u(x, y), v(x, y))$, where u and v are spatially varying components of a vector field and (x, y) are pixel positions in an image. The basic and defining equation of the optical flow constraint is

$$I(x, y, t) = I(x + u(x, y), y + v(x, y), t + \Delta t), \quad (3)$$

i.e., if the registration is correct, then the intensities in the two images should correspond. While we could write the two images as $I_1(x, y)$ and $I_2(x, y)$, it makes sense to consider the two images and the associated process that deforms the image as arising from a continuous parameter variation in image formation. We therefore maintain the original formulation in terms of a temporal image stack parameterized by (x, y, t) , where t is time and Δt is the discretization in time.

Consider a Taylor expansion of the video image stack

$$I(x + \Delta x, y + \Delta y, t + \Delta t) = I(x, y, t) + \frac{\partial I}{\partial x} \Big|_{(x,y,t)} \Delta x + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} \Big|_{(x,y,t)} \Delta y + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} \Big|_{(x,y,t)} \Delta t + \mathcal{O}(\Delta x^2, \Delta y^2, \Delta t^2). \quad (4)$$

Then, stopping the expansion at first order, the brightness constancy, or optical flow, constraint from Eq. 3 can be determined using local quantities derived from the image

intensity function I at (x, y, t) only:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I(x + \Delta x, y + \Delta y, t + \Delta t) - I(x, y, t) &= \\
 \frac{\partial I}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} \Delta y + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} \Delta t &= \\
 \frac{\partial I}{\partial x} \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} + \frac{\partial I}{\partial y} \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta t} + \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} &= 0. \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

The equation in the last row is known as the (linearized) optical flow constraint, or the optical flow equation. The unknown quantities $u(x, y) := \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta t} \Big|_{x,y,t}$ and $v(x, y) := \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta t} \Big|_{x,y,t}$ are seen to be the sought displacement vectors at every pixel in the image. Looking at a single pair of frames, the explicit time dependence on t can be dropped.

Since there are two unknowns, but only a single constraint, neighboring pixels typically stabilize the estimation. However, failure modes are the so-called aperture effect [22] that occurs if pronounced 1-dimensional structures (linear edges) are present in the image. In this case, the constraint does not determine a shift along the edge.

The two basic approaches to the solution of the optical flow equation are 1) local techniques, of which the most well-known example is the Lucas-Kanade tracker [21] that yield sparse estimates in the image, and 2) global techniques that seek to estimate dense correspondences between two frames. The prototypical example is the Horn and Schunck method [20] which forms the basis of most variational approaches to optical flow computation. 3) Recently, deep neural networks (DNNs) have had outstanding success in optical flow detection and dominate the benchmarks [23] today.

4.2 SAR Coregistration with Optical Flow

In the present paper, we evaluate the suitability of optical flow techniques to coregister SAR images that suffer from local distortions. For this, we choose the class of variational optical flow techniques [20] because they provide robust results and do not require training data. In this framework, the flow estimation is formulated as an energy minimization problem:

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{u,v} \int_{\Omega} \left\| \nabla I \cdot \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} - \frac{\partial I}{\partial t} \right\|_2^2 dx dy + \lambda \text{ prior}. \quad (6)$$

Here, ∇I and $\frac{\partial I}{\partial t}$ are known image-space derivatives that are computed by image filtering operations [24], and Ω is the image domain used for registration. We use the whole image in our experiments. The first term encodes the optical flow constraint, Eq. 5, whereas the term ‘‘priors’’ encodes additional knowledge about the displacement fields $u(x, y)$ and $v(x, y)$ and λ is a scalar user-tunable parameter regulating the strength with which the prior information will be used. A common choice of prior is

$$\text{prior} = \int_{\Omega} \left\| \sqrt{u^2 + v^2} \right\|_1 dx dy, \quad (7)$$

also known as the L2L1-norm. The effect of this term is that jump discontinuities in the estimated flow fields

are permitted, which is a likely feature of SAR images, e.g. if buildings are present. A detailed description of the TV-L1 algorithm that we employ for our experiments is given in [16]. Note that solvers also typically implement a coarse-to-fine strategy to estimate displacement vectors in a larger range than 1-2pixels [25]: since the optical flow equation Eq. 5 is linearized, it is only valid for small displacements. Other pre-processing tricks include a normalization of the images and more [25].

5 Results

We apply the TV-L1 optical flow estimation algorithm [16] to Track 1 and Track 2 of the airborne dataset. For large

Figure 5 Calculated displacement in range direction for track 1 and track 2.

vertical baselines the displacement in range is mostly influenced by the different heights within the scene. Fig. 5 shows the map of displacements of the images obtained by using data of the first and second trajectory, which strongly corresponds to the local heights taken from a DEM of the scene (not shown). The orientation is the same as seen in Fig. 4. The shifts in the azimuth direction result from imperfections of the individual flown trajectories as compared to the reference trajectory (shown in Fig. 6).

Note that the lengths of the arrows in Fig. 6 are scaled by a factor of 20 for visualization purposes. The Figure illustrates the direction and length ratios of the shifting vectors calculated by optical flow.

In Fig. 7 we depict the improvement of coherence after coregistration using the proposed method.

6 Conclusion

The given airborne tracks lack good correlation as observed in the coherence matrix. As previously mentioned, conventional intensity-based algorithms which involve correlation for coregistration will not directly work on the

Figure 6 Vector field of the SAR dataset obtained using optical flow [16].

Figure 7 Coherence of the SAR dataset before and after coregistration

dataset. Hence, we investigate the applicability of optical flow techniques from computer vision for coregistration of the dataset. We find that coregistration of SAR images with optical flow techniques is robust against sensor imperfections and can solve the coregistration problem even in the presence of strong non-local deformations. We, therefore, see great promise in the further study of these techniques for the processing of SAR data.

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7 Literature

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